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MISAMIS UNIVERSITY RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

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Principal Investigator

MUREC Code 2025-082

**THE USE OF MULTISENSORY APPROACHES TO READING INSTRUCTION: AN
APPRECIATIVE INQUIRY**

Dear Investigator:

The MU Research Ethics Committee (MUREC), upon review of your research protocol, found no risk to the research participants, hence recommending **APPROVAL**. You may proceed with gathering data for your study.

However, the following are the recommendations based on the review by the Committee:

- For Statement of the Problem, recheck the alignment of the research questions with the questions in the Interview Guide.
- For Participants, indicate the number of years of the participants' teaching experience.
- For Ethical Considerations, indicate that the participants may decline at any time or any point in the interviews.
- Remove the statement mentioning that the future research output is for publication.

Sincerely yours,

HAYDEE D. VILLANUEVA, PhD

Chair, MUREC